

Performance of a Vortex Tube (Ranque-Hilsch)

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Abstract—This experimental paper aims to measure the performance of a small-size vortex tube experimental kit from Meech. The work has been done as a part of my Bachelor of Engineering Honours degree during my honors project in 2021-2022. The velocity and temperature for each generator have been measured. The comparison between the fully open, partially open, and fully closed control valve has been made for one generator and the cold fraction and COP have been calculated.

Index Terms—Ranque-Hilsch, Vortex Tube, Thermodynamics, COP, Vortex, Air

I. INTRODUCTION

A vortex tube, also called a Ranque-Hilsch tube, is an instantaneous thermodynamic system. By supplying compressed air at ambient temperature and pressure of about 7 to 8 bar at the inlet, the bidirectional vortex tube (fig.1) [1] produces two air flows at different temperatures in each outlet. The first one is colder and the second one is hotter than the inlet [2].

Fig. 1. Bidirectional Vortex Tube

The air goes through a vortex spin chamber (fig.1) and is injected tangentially by one or more nozzles to allow a rotation called "vortex" alongside the tube axis. The air goes toward the control valve. The hotter the gas, the farther it is from the center of the tube. Around point "4", the hot air exits the tube while the colder air at the center is reflected by the valve and goes toward point "5". It allows a counter-flow between two different density fluids. The cold air leaves at point "5". The vortex tube has no moving parts which make it reliable, low in

maintenance cost and also no need for refrigerants [3]. Vortex tube is still fairly unknown. Most people do not know what a vortex tube is and its use of it. Having a better understanding and showing to industries that this system exists is crucial.

II. METHODS

By using a small vortex tube experimental kit from Meech [4] containing a small vortex tube plus eight plastic generators with different properties, the velocity and temperature have been measured for each generator. To determine the temperature, thermocouples have been mounted at each exit and linked to Squirrel View to measure and read the data. More variation in temperature can be seen when the pressure at the inlet increases. The inlet temperature has been considered as equal to the ambient temperature (18°C) by considering that the time between the compression and the release is huge enough. A speed meter has been used to determine the velocity at each outlet by using a blade that rotates due to the airflow. The assumption that all air goes through the blades to measure the speed has been made. The cold fraction has been calculated using a formula from [5] based on the calculated temperature. The optimal performance coefficient (COP) has been calculated from thermodynamics equations [6] by using the previous cold fractions and temperatures. A comparison between all the temperatures and velocity of all generators has been made to determine velocity, temperature, COP, DT and cold fraction. The heat capacities have been calculated from air-thermodynamics Excel spreadsheets in the function of the temperature and the pressure. This variation has been considered negligible for this range of temperature by increasing the error of 1/1000. A set of measures dependent on the valve opening has been done for the GREEN generator by the same method as previously and by turning the valve from fully open to fully closed.

III. RESULTS & ANALYSIS

Cold and hot outlet temperatures for each generator (fig.2) are plotted. Each generator has a different size illustrated by a number followed by a letter. These generators are rated from 10 to 35 Cubic Feet per Minute (cfm) at 80

Pounds per Square Inch (psi). Each color has its own size (tab.I). The letter "H" (high cold fraction) generators are designed for maximum refrigeration and "L" generators are designed to produce the lowest possible temperature [7]. For the same size, The "H" type shows a smaller ΔT than the "L" type. For the same type of generator, the higher the cfm, the higher the hot temperature, the lower the cold temperature. The velocity needs to be carefully interpreted due to the low accuracy of the method. The speed (fig.3) is always higher on the hot side than the cold one. This is due to the cross-section which is also smaller in the cold size. Higher is the cfm, higher is the speed. According to Bernoulli's law, when the flow rate increases with the same section, the speed increases. The error of measurement of both thermocouples is negligible.

Fig. 2. Temperature measurement by Generator Type

Fig. 3. Speed Measurement by Generator Type

All the data (tab.I) for each generator have been summarised. The cold fraction is proportional to the cfm. For the same cfm, the "L" type has a lower cold fraction. The COP (fig.4) is proportional to the cold fraction and is also higher at the same cfm for the "H" type. Velocity and temperature in function of the valve closing (fig.II) for both sides with the GREEN generator were summarised. The valve is always on the hot side. When the valve has been closed at 50%, no temperature change has been detected. However the velocity at the cold inlet has been increasing by a factor of 0.24 while the hot size decreasing by a factor of 0.17. at 0% open, no more flow goes through the hot outlet and the velocity at the cold size has been increasing by a factor 0.74. The temperature has been

Fig. 4. COP evolution in function of the cold fraction

increasing by 18 °C. The greater the cold fraction, the greater the COP, more energy is available for the purpose of cooling or heating compared to the required energy of the compression system.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, Both the temperature and velocity of each generator for the hot and cold sizes have been measured. The cold fraction and COP have also been calculated. The COP is dependent on the cold fraction and the size of the generator. The higher the generator and vortex tube size, the higher the COP and the delivered power. These results need to be carefully interpreted especially with the speed measurement due to the accuracy of the method. Further works need to be done i.e. including other generators for the valve closing experimentation or comparing all the data with a bigger vortex tube. The vortex tube is highly used in industry for electronic cooling and highly explosive atmosphere which makes it really useful. It can also be mounted in series. However it is only used for local cooling or heating. Using this technology for a wider space such as a house heating system is not possible due to the low power.

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TABLE I
DATA SUMMARY

Colour	Size	Tin [°C]	Tc [°C]	Th [°C]	μ_f	COP	dT [°C]
GREEN	10L	18	-28	30	0.2069	0.1742	58
WHITE	15L	18	-24	33	0.2632	0.2252	57
RED	15H	18	-24	39	0.3334	0.2852	63
GREY	25L	18	-17	37	0.3519	0.3095	54
BLUE	25H	18	-7	33	0.3750	0.3428	40
BEIGE	35H	18	-6	32	0.3684	0.3380	38
YELLOW	10H	18	-20	29	0.2245	0.1952	49
BROWN	35L	18	-1	42	0.5581	0.5217	43

TABLE II
VALVE OPENING MEASURE FOR THE GREEN GENERATOR

	100 % open		50 % open		0 % open	
	Cold	Hot	Cold	Hot	Cold	Hot
Velocity (m/s)	1.9	12	2.5	10	7.2	0
Temperature (°C)	-28	30	-28	31	-10	0